

Urban Gendered Spaces: A Spatial Perspective to Sexual Crimes

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Summary

This study investigates the spatial distribution of sexual crimes in the West End of Newcastle upon Tyne, UK, an area characterised by ethnic diversity, high crime rates and economic deprivation. Using spatial analysis, the research identifies crime hotspots and reveals that spaces adjacent to barbershops and grocery stores are particularly vulnerable. These locations, associated with higher ethnic diversity and evolving social dynamics, have transitioned into male-dominated gathering spaces, correlating with patterns of gender-based offences. The findings offer critical insights into the relationship between urban socio-cultural dynamics and crime, contributing to strategies for enhancing urban safety and fostering community resilience.

KEYWORDS: Gendered space, Crime data, Space Syntax, Urban analytics, Urban equality

1. Introduction

Sexual crimes in public urban settings, such as streets and parks, remain a critical issue in the UK. Recent data from a survey commissioned by the British Transport Police (BTP, 2023) reveals that over one-third of women have experienced sexual harassment or offences while commuting on trains or buses. This highlights the pressing need for improved safety measures and public awareness to address the risks faced by women in these environments. Public outrage over these issues has been intensified by high-profile cases exposing systemic shortcomings.

Recent research underscores the influence of urban infrastructure on crime locations, including rapes and sexual offences. Offenders often exploit secluded areas like parks and back alleys as concealment sites (Polko & Kimic, 2022; Myhill and Allen, 2002). Additional studies suggest that urban amenities like metro stations, bars, and restaurants may inadvertently contribute to sexual crime patterns by increasing foot traffic and creating potential hotspots (Lundrigan et al., 2024; Jiang et al., 2024; Ceccato, 2014). However, much of the existing literature lacks a nuanced analysis of local contextual factors that may establish clearer causal links between these amenities and crime occurrences. This gap underscores the need for more localised studies to understand the interplay between urban design and public safety.

This study investigates the spatial distribution of sexual crimes in the West End of Newcastle upon Tyne, a region deeply affected by de-industrialisation. The decline of industry has led to high unemployment and economic deprivation, further compounded by the growth of economically

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disadvantaged ethnic minority communities. The research introduces the concept of 'Urban Gendered Space', communal areas shaped by local socio-demographics and predominantly associated with one gender. By analysing the relationship between these spaces and patterns of sexual crime, the study illuminates their impact on urban safety dynamics. The findings offer valuable insights for developing strategies to create more inclusive and secure public spaces.

2. Study Area

The West End of Newcastle is home to some of the city's most diverse neighbourhoods, such as Arthur's Hill, Benwell, and Elswick, where residents represent a broad spectrum of cultural and ethnic backgrounds. However, recent data reveals that crime rates in these areas are significantly higher compared to other non-city centre neighbourhoods, especially concerning harassment and violence against women (Figure 1). The area has long been associated with criminal activity and social challenges, with certain 'hotspots', such as Elswick Park, being described as dangerous "no-go zones" after dark. As a result, women in these neighbourhoods often limit their access to public spaces due to safety concerns. This situation highlights the need for a deeper understanding of the socio-demographic factors that contribute to these patterns of fear and crime.

Figure 1 Annual sexual crime occurrence per LSOA

3. Methods

3.1. Data

The sexual offence data for this study was obtained from *police.uk*, an open-source database for police service and information (POLICE.UK, 2024). The crime types cover sexual assault and unlawful (underage) sexual intercourse, rape and exposure. It contains details such as the date, time, geographical coordinates, and the Lower Layer Super Output Areas (LSOAs) where the crimes occurred. The data, covering the period from April 2023 to April 2024, was filtered to exclude offences that did not occur in open spaces. Urban built environment data, including road layouts and Points of Interest (POI), were sourced from OpenStreetMap using the *QuickOSM* plugin in QGIS, while urban green space data was obtained from the OS Open Greenspace database (Ordnance Survey, 2024).

3.2. Analytics

First, Kernel Density Estimation (KDE) was applied using QGIS to identify crime hotspots (Mission, 2024). KDE is a widely recognised non-parametric technique for spatial data analysis (Jiang et al., 2024). Next, the distances between each crime location and the nearest Points of Interest (POIs) including public green spaces, pubs, restaurants, barbershops, and grocery stores—were calculated. The proportion of distances under 200 metres was measured, as this threshold reflects the typical human sight range and characterises neighbourhood-scale environmental features within a short walking distance (Huang et al., 2022; Villanueva et al., 2014). Finally, Space Syntax analysis is conducted using the *QGIS space syntax toolkit* (Gil et al., 2023) to assess spatial configurations and their influence on crime pattern. Two key metrics were utilised: Integration (INT), which measures how well streets are connected within the network and their potential to facilitate pedestrian movement and accessibility, and Total Depth (TD), which quantifies the cumulative distance from a specific street segment to all other segments in the network (Shpuza, 2014; Nag et al., 2022).

4. Result

Figure 2 illustrates the spatial overlap between the KDE of annual sexual crimes and the locations of barbershops and grocery stores, emphasising areas with high concentrations of crime. Notably, the KDE values are significantly higher in zones where barbershops and grocery stores are co-located, suggesting these spaces act as focal points for crime occurrences. Figures 3a and 3b delve deeper into this relationship by presenting the distributions of distances between crime locations and their nearest barbershop and grocery store respectively. The analysis reveals a strong spatial proximity, with the majority of crime locations situated less than 200 meters from these establishments. This pattern is quantitatively reinforced in Figure 4, which shows that 53% of crimes occur within 200 meters of a barbershop, while 68% are within the same distance of a grocery store. By comparison, only 40% of crimes occur within 200 meters of a restaurant, and the percentages are even lower for pubs and public green spaces, at 17% each. These findings highlight the distinct spatial dynamics surrounding barbershops and grocery stores, which appear to play a more central role in the environmental and social fabric of these neighbourhoods, functioning as Urban Gendered Spaces.

Figure 2 Kernel Density Estimation (KDE) of annual sexual crime and locations of barbershops and groceries

Figure 3 (a) Histogram of distance (m) between crime location and nearest barber; (b) Histogram of distance (m) between crime location and nearest grocery

Figure 4 Percentage of POI within 200m of crime location

In the final step, Space Syntax analysis was conducted, and the results are presented in Figures 5 and 6. The findings indicate that sexual crime hotspots are typically situated near, but not directly on, the most accessible streets, such as the high street, which exhibits the highest INT and the lowest TD. Instead, crimes tend to occur on streets with slightly lower accessibility, such as back alleys adjacent to the high street. This pattern is further corroborated by Figure 7, which illustrates crime rates per street segment grouped by INT and TD values. As shown in Figures 7a and 7b, street segments with the second-highest INT (1,300–1,500) and the second-lowest TD (50,000–60,000) experience the highest crime rates per segment. These results reinforce the correlation between accessibility and crime occurrence, suggesting that moderately accessible streets—close enough to attract movement but less visible or monitored—may present higher risks for criminal activity.

Figure 5 Street Integration (INT) and crime location

Figure 6 Street Total Depth (TD) and crime location

Figure 7 (a) Crimes per street sector grouped by Street Integration (INT); (b) Crimes per street sector grouped by Street Total Depth (TD)

5. Conclusion

This study employed spatial analysis techniques to explore the relationship between sexual offences and urban environmental factors, revealing patterns shaped by the area's diverse ethnic and demographic characteristics. Traditional masculine spaces such as pubs, were found to have limited influence, likely due to the predominantly non-drinking cultural background of the local population in the West End. Instead, emerging "urban gendered spaces", such as barbershops and grocery stores - frequented by men - show significant associations with sexual offences. The co-existence of these spaces appears to contribute to the context in which these crimes occur. Space Syntax analysis further demonstrated that crime hotspots are typically found in less visible, and often poorly lit back alleys. These findings underscore the crucial role of both the physical environment and the accessibility of urban spaces in influencing the distribution of sexual crimes. This study provides valuable insights for urban planning and crime prevention strategies, emphasising the need for targeted interventions in specific spatial contexts. However, this study acknowledges certain limitations. The data on sexual offences was sourced exclusively from police records, which often fail to capture the full extent and complexity of gender-related crimes. Future research should delve deeper into specific categories of sexual offences, such as sexual assault, stalking or rape, and consider demographic and socioeconomic characteristics of both offenders and victims, including age and gender. A more comprehensive approach that integrates qualitative data and broader societal contexts will be essential for advancing understanding in this field.

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Biographies

Dr. Mingyu Zhu is a Research Associate at the Urban Big Data Centre at the University of Glasgow. His research interests encompass the design, construction, and operation of the urban built environment, with a focus on GeoBIM, Model-Based Systems Engineering (MBSE), and Human-Computer Interaction (HCI). He is particularly interested in cross-disciplinary collaborations that bridge engineering, social science, and art & design

Dr. Jiayi Jin is an Assistant Professor of Architecture at Northumbria University. She leads the 'Gender-inclusive Cities' project (PI, 2022–present), which explores the conceptualisation and experience of urban design and planning through a gender lens. Since 2023, Dr. Jiayi Jin has been collaborating with Dr. Lucy Grimshaw on the project #WomenSpatialActivism: Exploring the connection between urban

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Dr. Lucy Grimshaw is an Assistant Professor of Social Work, Education and Community Wellbeing at Northumbria University. Lucy is committed to improving education spaces and providing opportunities for groups which are often marginalised and discriminated against. She leads training and research initiatives focused on gender-based violence and addressing the specific needs of pregnant students and students with children.